

Implementation strategies for EEG processing on multi-GPU computing systems

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Abstract: Most EEG processing algorithms are very time-consuming due to the large amount of EEG data to be processed and the complexity of the algorithms required. Multi-GPU systems are ideal candidates to accelerate EEG processing tasks thanks to their high compute performance and support for massively parallel execution. However, developing multi-GPU programs is a difficult task and various overheads can reduce the final program performance. In this paper, we investigate the performance effects of various memory access implementation patterns for multi-GPU EEG algorithms and recommend strategies with the best performance to be used for large-scale EEG processing.

Introduction

EEG signals contain a wealth of physiological and pathological information about the activity of the human brain [1]. In order to extract these and understand better how the human brain works, various processing methods, such as filtering, signal decomposition, time-frequency and connectivity analysis [2], etc. might be necessary. Unfortunately, these EEG processing methods are time-consuming due to (i) high sampling rates (up to several kHz), (ii) large number of electrodes and (iii) the demand to increase the number of subjects in experiments. Experiment processing times often reach days [3]; therefore execution speed and efficiency are of paramount importance.

Traditional EEG processing based on MATLAB scripts executed on CPUs cannot achieve high enough execution speed [4]. Modern supercomputers contain hundreds to thousands of accelerator cards (GPUs) that seem to be ideal for speeding up EEG processing. To date, however, not many EEG processing implementations are available for single GPUs [5]–[7], let alone multi-GPU systems. The main reason is that the design and implementation of efficient multi-GPU parallel programs is a great challenge.

This paper investigates how to simplify multi-GPU programs while keeping the computational performance high. First, we give a brief overview

of heterogeneous CPU-GPU systems, GPU programming fundamentals and abstractions, then study different data transfer implementation strategies. Based on benchmarking results, we provide recommendations for developers to help developing highly efficient multi-GPU programs.

Methods

Heterogeneous computing systems

Multi-GPU systems belong to the class of heterogeneous systems that contain multi-core CPUs and GPUs [8], each with its own separate physical memory. The host system (CPU) runs the main program that controls the execution on the host and on the accelerator device (GPU). The host and the device are connected via the PCI-Express bus. The CUDA programming model enables users to execute applications on heterogeneous computing systems. A typical CUDA program consists of five main steps: (i) allocating space for data in GPU memory, (ii) copying data from CPU to GPU memory, (iii) invoking the CUDA kernel to perform program-specific parallel computation, (iv) copying data back from GPU to CPU memory, and finally, (v) deallocating host and device memory areas. As shown in Figure 1, the main program is executed on the host, while the parallel kernel code is executed on the GPU device. GPU kernel execution is asynchronous to the host; the host and device can execute instructions simultaneously, and explicit synchronization is required to ensure that GPU execution is finished before proceeding with the execution of subsequent program steps.

Figure 1. CUDA program structure and its heterogeneous execution.

In heterogeneous computing systems, data transfer between CPU and GPU memories is unavoidable. The low bandwidth of the PCI-Express bus compared to that of the GPU RAM results in non-negligible communication overhead that can easily dominate execution time if copy operations are used excessively. The number one rule in GPU programming is to minimize data transfer between CPU and GPU, but explicit memory and data management is a complex and error-prone develop task. The problem is aggravated if we use multi-GPU systems in which we need to manage data partitioning and distribution, too.

Memory access patterns

The CUDA programming model provides different levels of abstraction and system support for performing memory copy/data transfer operations, such as:

- explicit, low-level memory management and data copy functions;
- Unified Memory providing a single continuous address space for host and GPU memory;
- Unified Virtual Addressing (UVA), a virtual memory system enabling users to expand the available GPU memory size ; and
- Peer-to-Peer access mechanism that provides direct memory access between GPU devices over PCI-e or NVLink communication channels.

In the followings, we describe how these abstractions can be used to create generic memory access patterns for multi-GPU EEG program implementations.

Explicit management and copy (Pattern 1) represents the lowest-level of CUDA programming interface and execution pattern, following the program structure shown in Figure 1. First we allocate memory for the input and output EEG signals on the CPU side then on each GPU, respectively. Before executing the EEG processing kernel functions, an explicit copy operation is required to copy one segment of the host input data to the corresponding GPU memory. After kernel execution, the result is copied back to the host memory. The data organization in the host and device memories and the various copy paths in this pattern are illustrated in Figure 2.

Unified Virtual Addressing (Pattern 2a) enables host memory and device memory to share a single virtual address space [9]. In pattern 1, we had to manage separate pointers to host and device memory, respectively. Using UVA, the memory space referenced by a pointer becomes transparent to

application code, i.e., pointers returned in UVA can be passed directly to kernel or host functions.

Figure 2. Memory access pattern 1, based on explicit low-level memory management.

Unified Memory (Pattern 2b) creates a pool of managed memory, where each allocation from this memory pool is accessible from both host and device size via the same memory address [10]. The underlying memory management system automatically migrates data in the unified memory space on-demand between the physical host and device memories, freeing the programmer from the burden of explicit copy operations. Data migration is transparent to the application, which can greatly simplify programming and improve performance.

Figure 3. Memory access pattern 2, based on Unified Memory and UVA.

Unified Memory depends on UVA support, but the two are entirely different technologies. UVA provides a single virtual memory address space

for all processors in the system but it does not automatically migrate data from one physical location to another; that is a capability unique to Unified Memory. Using either UVA or Unified Memory, as shown in Figure 3, we only need to assign two unified addresses (pointers) to the input and output signals respectively. These two addresses are visible to both the host and the device, so different GPUs can directly access the input data and store the processed data back to the unified address pointing to the output signal.

Peer-to-Peer access (Pattern 3) enables GPUs to access each other’s memory directly via load/store operations via the PCI-e or NVLink communication channels without CPU involvement and additional device-host memory transfers [9]. NVLink is a proprietary high-speed point-to-point serial communication technology for connecting GPUs directly. In this pattern, kernel functions can directly reference data stored in remote GPU device memories. Transparently to the kernel, the referenced remote data will be transferred over the NVLink or PCI-e bus to the requesting kernel thread. As shown in Figure 4, in this pattern, we explicitly copy the input data allocated on the host side to GPU0. The other GPUs obtain data directly from GPU0 via peer-to-peer access and store the processed results back to the device memory of GPU0 after completing the computation. As the final step, results stored in the memory of GPU0 are copied back to the host memory.

Figure 4. Memory access pattern 3, based on multi-GPU peer-to-peer access.

Benchmarking

We implemented a small set of representative EEG operations for benchmarking the performance of the four memory access patterns. For each pattern, we measured the execution time as a function of data size to

characterize the effect of data transfer on performance and simultaneously compared the complexity of the source code required for the different implementations.

Execution time for the full program including data copies and kernel executions was measured. In Pattern 1 and 3, this included explicit data copy steps. In Pattern 2 and 2b, the kernel execution time -- as shown in Fig 5 -- includes the implicit data copy/migration time as well, therefore the execution time of the kernels was also measured. In Pattern 1 and 3, the kernel execution times can be used as a baseline to measure how close we are to the ideal performance.

All multi-GPU benchmarking operations were performed on the 16-GPU (V100) HGX-2 NVIDIA server node operated in the IMEC GPULab (Ghent, Belgium).

Figure 5. Execution time measurement strategy for the different memory access patterns

Results

Execution time

The execution time of the EEG processing program was first measured using a fixed size data input. We were looking at how the execution time varies from one repetition of the program to another, showing effects of potential run-time optimisations. The program was executed repeatedly ten times for each memory access patterns. As shown in Fig 6, the first execution of Patterns 2a and 2b took a relatively longer time, implying that for the

remaining runs the input data has been already migrated to the GPU. The overall results show that the explicit management (Pattern 1) takes the longest time if the data is copied back and forth between the host and device for each kernel execution. If only one host-device data copy is required for a series of kernels, this pattern reaches near ideal (kernel only) performance level.

Pattern 2b (Unified Memory) achieved the best performance, eliminating the cost of data movement for repeated runs. This is followed in performance by Pattern 2a (UVA) that adds a fix overhead of the Virtual Shared Memory implementation. The worst performance is achieved with Pattern 3 where data is copied remotely via NVLink from GPU0 to the others.

Figure 6. Program execution times for the different memory access patterns.

Data size affects

During program execution, the Unified Memory will automatically migrate data from one physical location to another, but the UVA will not. Since this automatic process is transparent for kernel functions, we further tested the performance of Pattern 2a and 2b under different data sizes. Figure 7 shows the execution time of the Unified Memory and UVA patterns for different data sizes (varying from 4GB to 32GB). The execution was also repeated 10 times for each size to calculate the average execution time. Since the first execution always took longer, that is shown separately. As seen in Figure 7, the Unified Memory based pattern (Pattern 2b) is about 80 times faster on

average. For the very first execution of the program, the Unified Memory version is approximately 2-3 times faster than the UVA implementation.

Figure 7. Execution times of Pattern 2a (UVA) and 2b (Unified Memory) for varying data sizes.

Conclusions

We designed and implemented different memory access patterns for multi-GPU EEG processing algorithms based on the different memory programming abstractions provided by NVIDIA CUDA. A set of illustrative EEG processing programs were implemented using these patterns, then benchmarked on a V100 GPU based multi-GPU server. The performance results of the different memory access patterns show that the Unified Memory access pattern achieved the best results in maximizing performance and reducing program complexity. We further tested the performance of Unified-Memory-based pattern and UVA-based pattern with different data sizes. The results showed that for the EEG processing algorithms that require a large number of repetitions, Unified Memory can be especially advantageous. As the next stage of our research, we will implement a full-function EEG processing pipeline for multi-GPU systems that can enable researchers to execute large-scale EEG studies efficiently on accelerated supercomputers.

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